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Praise be to the
Almighty!

Preface

The Centre for Publication Ethics, Savitribai Phule Pune University studied 5484 publications (India), 6233 (South Asia) and 34907 (East Asia) in the disciplines such as languages, literature, philosophy, history, etc. The study was based on the Web of Science database for the years 1989 – 2020 and the results were announced. According to its report on 'Arts and Humanities Research in India, South Asia and East India, the University of Hyderabad is ranked 3 among the Indian Universities. It bagged the 'University of the Year Award' recently from the Federation of Indian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (FICCI) at the Higher Education Excellence Awards Programme held in New Delhi. Dr. Pramod K. Nayar, Professor of English, University of Hyderabad received the Award as Chairman of Institution of Eminence (IoE).

The report shows that Dr. K. Narayana Chandran, Professor of English, University of Hyderabad (UoH) and Dr. Pramod K. Nayar, Professor of English, (UoH) are among Asia's top twenty Arts and Humanities Researchers. Prof. K. Narayan occupies the 1st position in India and South Asia. He is ranked 9 in South and East Asia. Dr. Pramod K. Nayar is at 3 in India and South Asia. He is placed at 18 in South and East Asia. The Editorial Board congratulates on the distinction of the two top researchers of the University of Hyderabad.

I am delighted to release Volume VII, No. 1 of Sadakath: A Research Bulletin. I believe that the 15 research articles being published in this Volume will contribute to take up innovative research projects and studies in such disciplines as Arts and Humanities and Sciences. I thank profusely the authors and the co-authors for their scholarly contributions.

On behalf of the Editorial Board, I express my thankfulness to our Honourable Secretary and Correspondent Alhaj. T.E.S. Fathu Rabbani for sanctioning funds to launch this Volume. I thank sincerely our Principal Dr. M. Mohamed Sathik, Dr. A. Abdul Kader,

Director of Unaided Courses; Dr. K. Senthamarai Kannan, Director, Centre for Research and Head, Department of Statistics, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli; Dr. D. Muhammad Noorul Mubarak, Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science, University of Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram; Dr. S. Srinivasa Ragavan, Professor and Head, Department of Library and Information Science, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapalli, and Dr. A. Jahir Hussain, Assistant Professor, Department of Arabic, University of Madras, Chennai for their moral support. My thanks are due to the respective Heads of the Departments of our College who scrutinised and recommended the research papers for publication.

I place on record my sincere thanks to Dr. K. Hema, Editor, for having checked and proofread the write-ups. I am grateful to Dr. R.R. Saravana Kumar, the Convener and the Editors and Technical Editors, Dr. S. Mahadevan; Dr. A.H. Mohideen Badshah; Dr. S.M. Abdul Kader; Dr. A. Syed Mohamed; Dr. S. Syed Ali Fathima; Mr. J. Ubaiyathullah; Dr. M.I. Zahir Hussain; Dr. S. Shajun Nisha; Mr. S.M.A. Khaleelur Rahman and Dr. A. Hamil for their enthusiastic support to release the Volume. It immensely pleases me to thank Ms. A. Ameenal for having extended personal and technical support for bringing out this multidisciplinary research journal.

The Editorial Board encourages the readers to offer their insights and observations to better our initiatives towards promoting genuine and quality research.

1 June 2019
Tirunelveli.

Chief Editor

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A Comparative Study of Service Quality and Customer Loyalty in Indian Banking Sector

Abdul Rahuman, M.¹

Abstract

The Indian Banking sector has resulted in a number of innovations in order to improve their service quality and customer loyalty. This has provided customers with an opportunity to compare and select a bank that ultimately provides services that satisfy them. Therefore, the main aim of the study is to understand the relationship between the service quality and customer loyalty, the resultant customer satisfaction for both public sector and private sector banks in Tirunelveli City. The paper utilised a quantitative survey design for the dimensions of service quality and customer loyalty which were considered as variables for the study using Likert scale. In some aspects both public and private banks need to concentrate on service quality and customer loyalty. The survey declares that in comparison public sector bank customers are satisfied with regard to service quality and customer loyalty . However, the study also suggests that public sector banks concentrate to take more steps on private sector banks in this regard.

Keywords: *Customer Satisfaction, Service quality, Customer loyalty*

Introduction:

Today, Banking sectors have become a very essential part of our life. Banks cater to the needs of agriculturists, traders, industrialists, professionals, entrepreneurs, and to all the other categories of the public. Nowadays banks concentrate on customer benefits to retain their satisfaction. The banking system is a driver for the economic development of any country, as it plays a main role in diverting the idle capital resources towards an effective utilization. At present, banking sector is more customer-oriented. The major challenges faced by banks today are as to how to cope with competitive forces and strengthen their services. Hence, in recent times, provision of service quality and customer loyalty has become one of the focal points in the service agenda of banks.

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Service quality:

Service quality is very essential for the development and growth of banking sector. In the past, quality was measured only for the some tangible aspects because of low dominance of banking sector in the economy. Nowadays it has increased, the measurement of service quality become a very important one, because Indian banking sector has suddenly witnessed to play a major role in the development of our country. Measuring the service quality of banking sector is very difficult because there are more number of competitors. Its leads the customers taste and preference also changed every time. The paper is a survey of the service quality of select public and private sector banks and the customer satisfaction towards the services offered by the selected banks.

Customer Loyalty:

Customer loyalty is positively related to customer satisfaction as happy customers consistently favour the brands that meet their needs. Every supplier wants to create and retain a loyal customer who engages in continued profitable business with him. Loyal customers are purchasing a firm's products, or services exclusively, and they are not willing to switch their preferences over a competitive firm. Customer Loyalty is the measure of success of the supplier in retaining a long-term relationship with the customer. Thus, customer loyalty is attained when a supplier receives the ultimate reward of his efforts in interacting with its customer. The loyalty may be product specific, or it may be a company specific.

Objectives of the Study:

The objective of the study is to identify the level of satisfaction of the service quality and customer loyalty of the selected public sector and private sector banks in Tirunelveli city.

Collection of Data:

In the study both primary and secondary data have been collected .The research was conducted using a questionnaire designed to understand the banking services provided Tirunelveli city customers. For the study, a structured questionnaire was developed in two stages. In the first stage, an exploratory study was conducted using personal and focus group interviews. In the second stage, based on exploratory study, a five-point Likert scale was conducted.

Sample Technique:

Simple random sampling method was applied to collect data from customers of State Bank of India, and Indian Overseas Bank. The customers were taken from public sector banks,

whereas Karur Vysya Bank, and Tamil Nadu Mercandile Bank customers were taken from private sector banks.

Satisfaction of Public Sector Bank Customers towards Service Quality and Customer Loyalty:

To get response from public the select sector bank customers a total number of 120 questionnaires were circulated. Out of the total sample size, 100 customers who availed of the banking services were taken. The collection of data began in the month of October, 2018 and was completed in November, 2018.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Customer Satisfaction Regarding Service Quality

Sl. No.	Particulars	Respondents' Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted Score	Total score	Percentile points
1.	Physical appearance of the bank is neat	33	19	10	13	25	322	500	64.4
2.	Sufficient seating arrangement	35	17	12	15	21	330	500	66
3.	Reliable information	28	22	16	14	20	324	500	64.8
4.	Quick and efficient service	16	12	20	30	22	270	500	54
5.	Less waiting time	10	13	26	34	17	265	500	53
6.	Employees at my bank treat me as a valued customer	12	15	24	22	27	263	500	52.6
7.	Confidentiality of my data	20	26	11	25	18	305	500	61
8.	Sense of Security	24	38	08	12	18	338	500	67.6

Sl. No.	Particulars	Respondents' Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted Score	Total score	Percentile points
9.	Fault free service	15	25	10	27	23	282	500	56.4
10.	Behavior and attitude of the employees	10	16	24	18	32	254	500	50.8

As per the above mentioned service quality calculation a total of 67.7. Sufficient seating arrangement is also fine with 66 percentile points

Table 2: Customer Satisfaction Regarding Customer Loyalty

Sl. No.	Particulars	Respondents' Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted score	Total score	Percentile points
1.	I recommend my bank to others	20	26	12	26	16	308	500	61.6
2.	I am seriously thinking about switch over to another bank	12	16	24	18	30	262	500	52.4
3.	It is easy to switch over to another bank	16	20	16	23	25	279	500	55.8
4.	I am willing to pay a higher price for a better product, or service	24	18	12	22	24	296	500	59.2
5.	I am a loyal customer	21	27	10	17	25	302	500	60.4

As per the above mentioned customer loyalty calculation a total of 61.6 percentile feel better over all the statement of “I recommend my bank to others”. The response “I am a loyal customer has scored 60.4 percentile points

Satisfaction of Private Sector Bank Customers towards Service Quality and Customer Loyalty:

To get response from private sector bank customers a total number of 124 questionnaires were circulated. Out of the total sample size, 100 customers who availed of the banking services were taken.

Table 3: Customer Satisfaction Regarding Service Quality

Sl. No.	Particulars	Respondents' Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted Score	Total Score	Percentile Points
1.	Physical appearance of the bank is neat	36	18	12	12	22	334	500	66.8
2.	Sufficient seating arrangement	38	14	12	17	19	335	500	67
3.	Reliable information	26	24	14	16	20	320	500	64
4.	Quick and efficient service	20	16	16	30	18	290	500	58
5.	Less waiting time	14	13	22	30	21	269	500	53.8
6.	Employees at my bank treat me as a valued customer	15	14	25	25	21	277	500	55.4
7.	confidentiality of my data	16	18	14	28	24	274	500	54.8
8.	Sense of Security	20	32	14	12	22	308	500	61.6

Sl. No.	Particulars	Respondents' Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted Score	Total Score	Percentile Points
9.	Fault free service	20	28	20	20	12	324	500	64.8
10.	Behavior and attitude of the employees	21	28	13	20	18	314	500	62.8

As per the above mentioned service quality calculation of private sector bank a total of 67 percentile feel better towards the sufficient seating arrangement. The factor physical appearance of the bank is neat has gained 66.8 percentile points

Table 4: Customer Satisfaction Regarding Customer Loyalty

Sl. No.	Particulars	Respondents' Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Weighted Score	Total Score	Percentile Points
1.	I recommend my bank to others	26	22	20	18	14	328	500	65.6
2.	I am seriously thinking about switching banks	10	14	28	20	28	258	500	51.6
3.	It is easy to switch bank	20	24	16	19	21	303	500	60.6
4.	I am willing to pay a higher price for a better product or service	30	22	10	20	18	344	500	68.8
5.	I am a loyal customer	26	24	11	19	20	317	500	63.4

As per the above mentioned customer loyalty calculation of private sector bank a total of 68.8 percentile feel better over the statement of "I am willing to pay a higher price for a better product or service". The response "I recommend my bank to others" has got 65.6 percentile points

Comparison of Public and Private Sector Banks

The following tables show the comparison of customer satisfaction regarding service quality and customer loyalty between public and private sector banks by combining their Likert scale percentile.

Table 5: Comparison of Service quality

Sl. No.	Service Quality	Public	Private
1.	Physical appearance of the bank is neat	64.4	66.8
2.	Sufficient seating arrangement	66	67
3.	Reliable information	64.8	64
4.	Quick and efficient service	54	58
5.	Less waiting time	53	53.8
6.	Employees at my bank treat me as a valued customer	52.6	55.4
7.	confidentiality of my data	61	54.8
8.	Sense of Security	67.6	61.6
9.	Fault free service	56.4	64.8
10.	Behavior and attitude of the employees	50.8	62.8

The customers of private sector banks are more satisfied with all the above mentioned service quality factors. The public sector banks ensure “Reliable information”, “confidentiality of the data” and “sense of security”.

Table 6: Comparison of Customer Loyalty

Sl. No.	Customer Loyalty	Public	Private
1.	I recommend my bank to others	61.6	65.6
2.	I am seriously thinking about switching over to another bank	52.4	51.6
3.	It is easy to switch over to another bank	55.8	60.6
4.	I am willing to pay a higher price for a better product, or service	59.2	68.8
5.	I am a loyal customer	60.4	63.4

The customers of private sector banks are more satisfied with most of the above mentioned factors with regard to customer loyalty.

Conclusion

Nowadays every bank provides a valuable service to their customers. Customers' taste and preference would differ from each other. Therefore, every bank must maintain a healthy relationship with their customers. The study concludes that the customers of private sector banks are more satisfied with regard to both service quality and customer loyalty. At the same time public sector banks enjoy the trust of the customers, but the private sector banks need to concentrate more on winning the hearts of their customers. The study is expected to help the bankers improve their customer service quality and loyalty in accordance with the expectations of their customers.

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